

Applying Thorndike's Theory Of Behavioural Learning To Music Education In A Regular Classroom

¹Doris Kelechi Ofili (Ph.D) & Dr. Precious A. Omuku²

^{1,2}Department of Music
University Of Port Harcourt, Port Harcourt, Nigeria
¹E-Mail: doris.ofili@uniport.edu.ng/08037094334
²E-Mail: precious.omuku@uniport.edu.ng/08038736025

ABSTRACT

Edward Thorndike is one of the most prominent proponents of learning theories. Thorndike's learning theory is based on stimulus-response. This simply means that for an object to respond to any action, that object has to be stimulated or motivated. Some researchers have done some expositions on the aforementioned theory especially on Thorndike's theory on "law of learning" which includes the law of readiness, the law of exercise and the law of effects. Research has proven that these laws are very crucial and significant to every music lessons in order to achieve an effective music studies at all level. The objective of the study is to bring to limelight the importance of exploring Thorndike's law of learning in music education. The study further discusses the implications of the theory to music teachers in regular classroom. The researcher explored primary methods in her data collection. The result from the findings was used to draw conclusion and recommendations.

Keywords: Thorndike's theory, music education, learning, classroom

INTRODUCTION

The major classification of learning theories is the stimulus-response and cognitive development theories. The study will be focusing on stimulus-response theory which is the basis of Edward Thorndike's learning theory. Hilgard and Bower (1975) reveals that "stimulus-response theories views learning more in terms of behavioural sequences, habit acquisition and trial and error" (p. 23). Edward Thorndike (1874-1949) believed in an actual, albeit in-defined connection between a stimulus and a response. Such a connection or bond could be established and strengthened by following a desired stimulus-response connection by a satisfying state of affairs. Consequently, the aforementioned theory is highly suitable for music education.

Music education is concerned with the teaching and learning of music. The teaching and learning of music cuts across all aspects of learning domains including cognitive, psychomotor and affective domain. Thorndike's theory of trial-error is vital in developing the three (3) aspects of learning domains. A regular classroom is a classroom that consists of three (3) levels of pupils/students, which include the gifted, the average and students below average which are often referred to as pupils/students with learning difficulties. These three (3) categories of learners respond differently to learning activities hence the reason for choosing the aforementioned theory for this study.

Some researcher's view or perception of Thorndike's theory especially in respect to his 'laws of learning' is highly educative and appreciable. They perceive the theory as an actual framework that should guide both learners and teachers in learning processes. Apparently, when the laws are applied to regular classroom music education, they make for an effective lesson.

Concept of Thorndike's Behavioural Theory

The major aim of learning theories as expressed by Ofili (2018) is “to emphasize the role of environmental influences in sharpening the way a person develops” (p. 60). In the views of the learning theories, “child development is guided by both deliberate and unintended learning experiences in the home, peer group, school and community. Therefore, childhood growth is significantly shaped by the efforts of parents, teachers, and others to socialize children in desirable ways (child development)”. According to learning theories, the same principles that explain how people can use a bicycle or computer also explains how children acquire social skills, emotional self-control, reasoning strategies, and the physical skills of walking and running.

Without a positive change in behavior, learning is said not to have occurred. There must be an observable change in behavior for learning to have taken place. The pupils/students could be taught through a model or observation. For example, learning to sing, dance or play a musical instrument by a student could be done by observing a teacher or tutor. The major classifications of learning theories are the ‘stimulus response’ (S-R) and cognitive theories. Hilgard (1975) in Onwuekwe (2014) opines that “stimulus response view learning more in terms of behavioural sequences habit acquisition and trial-error” (p.15).

Edward Thorndike's theory is known as trial and error. This theory emphasizes simple learning. Thorndike discourages complex learning. According to him, learning should be a product of reflexes. Man should learn in parts and learning is good and inevitable for man. Edward Thorndike believes that learning manifests by a change in behavior; that environment shapes the behavior of a child and that reinforcement arouses the child's interest to learn. He is of the opinion that learning is the acquisition of new behavior through trial and error.

Furthermore, Thorndike's theoretical construction was based on laboratory experiment using the puzzle box, a device for confining an animal, usually a cat, which can escape if it somehow pulls on a latch inside the box. Thorndike had a puzzle box and a hungry organism. The box was locked and the organism was inside the box. Thorndike placed food outside the box in a way that the food was visible but not accessible to the organism. The hungry animal made several efforts (trial and error) until accidentally, he pressed the button that opened the box and when the box opened, he jumped on the food and ate it. After eating the food, Thorndike sent the animal back to the puzzle box. After sometime, the animal became hungry again, he pressed the button and the box opened. The aim of the experiment was to see how organisms learn by doing. In this case, the organism learnt the appropriate button to press in order to open the box (Source: A Microsoft on the law of learning).

Thorndike's Laws of Learning

Edward Thorndike initiated three (3) important laws of learning which include:

- (i) Law of readiness
- (ii). Law of exercise and,
- (iii). Law of effect.

Thorndike's law of readiness is in relation to maturation. This law simply means to be ripened in order to function properly. It also means to develop the ability to perform works of different categories. The law means preparedness, the entry behavior to a new lesson. There are two types of readiness here. One refer to maturation while the other refers to acquisition of the necessary experience to serve as entry behavior to a new lesson.

The law of exercise according to Thorndike in Onwuekwe (2014) emphasizes the importance of practice which he said learners must do in order to learn. A learner must exercise, participate, explore, think, answer questions, write, sing and dance, etc. Learning by exercise is very significant as it encourages active and not passive learning. It promotes understanding through exploration. When a child is stimulated (stimulus), he responds or exercises (R). This gives us the S-R Bond. Listening is no learning but doing is the actual learning.

The law of effect as opined by Thorndike in Onwuekwe (2014) relates to the feedback after a response. In other words, he means the effect of the exercise performed by the learner; if this exercise attracts a failure or is not rewarded, that the effect is negative. An effective learning does not occur because the exercise will not be repeated. But if the exercise is rewarded, the S-R Bond is

Implications of Thorndike's Behavioural Theory on Music Education in a Regular Classroom

In respect to Thorndike's behavioural theory of learning, which is based on stimulus and response, this theory implies that something has to happen in order to cause something else to happen. For example, in the law of readiness, a child is expected to be prepared for a new lesson with respect to maturation and acquisition of necessary experiences. This refers to age and necessary skills that will facilitate learning. A child of three (3) years old is expected to be in Pre-nursery level, whose musical knowledge is expected to be limited to singing of nursery rhymes and poems rather than complex pieces. At that age, the child is not prepared for abstract or complex knowledge like musical notes, values, intervals, and so on. The child is meant to be fully matured and the necessary skills well developed and prepared for any given lesson in order for learning to be actualized. The pupils or students should be made to go from the known to the unknown. For example, starting with singing of nursery rhymes to simple hymns and then to choruses.

The law of exercise on the other hand according to Onwuekwe's analysis states that the learner must be given the opportunity and be made to do something in order to learn. There is a saying that practice makes perfect. Therefore, the more the pupils and students are given the opportunity or made to practice, the better they will perform the task. The more they practice to do something, either to sing, play an instrument, dance, read or write, etc, the more they learn and become perfect. The students must be made to exercise and participate in the lessons to ensure effective learning. If Thorndike had not given the puzzle the opportunity to keep exercising and making efforts in order to open the box, apparently the puzzle may not have learnt how to open the box on its own. Probably, it would have kept depending on Thorndike to always open the box for him to eat whenever he is hungry and eventually he would not have learnt how to open the box by himself. Teachers and tutors should always ensure that their students are actively involved in their lessons in order to achieve an effective lesson.

Lastly, the law of effect. This law is an essential aspect of learning. According to Onwuekwe, how does the teacher determine if a child is doing well, or even if the child will be able to ascertain that he/she is doing well or not? Without feedback, there is no assurance of effective learning. If a child is given an exercise, for example, a piece of music to sing or play, such exercise attracts either failure or reward. If the child fails, the child must not be humiliated or nicknamed, like many teachers will do but be given more opportunities to keep repeating each exercise until he/she is perfect and rewarded. If the exercise is rewarded, the child will be strengthened and will wish to do more but if it is not rewarded, the child's learning will be weakened and the child may lose interest. This theory encourages reinforcement in order to improve musical performance. The previous knowledge of the child must be put into consideration in order to arouse the child's interest for a new lesson (Source: Onwuekwe 2014: A Microsoft on Laws of Learning).

Implications of Thorndike's Theory for Music Teachers in Regular Classroom

Teachers are the bedrock of education. They are role models to their pupils and students and therefore, require all the necessary tools and knowledge they need to have an effective teaching experience. Edward Thorndike's laws of learning according to Viko (2015) which includes the "law of readiness, law of exercise and law of effect" (p. 36) should be strictly adhered to by music teachers in regular classroom. Thorndike's law of readiness implies that the pupils and students should be well prepared for the acquisition of new lessons. In other words, the entry behavior should be planned in such a way that it will be capable of arousing their interest for the new lesson, which will include moving from the known to the unknown. The lesson should be planned according to the age and knowledge level of the pupils and students in order to achieve the objective of the lesson.

Thorndike's law of exercise also proves what a learner must do in order to learn. This implies that the teachers must give the students the opportunity to exercise, participate, explore, think, answer questions, discuss, demonstrate, write, play, sing and dance, etc. No matter how dull you may assume a pupil or student to be, if given the opportunity to do all these, there could be a positive outcome. Learning by doing according to Onwuekwe (2014) "is very important because it encourages active and not passive learning. It promotes understanding through exploration. It helps the memory and makes for retention. When a child is stimulated (stimulus), he responds or exercises (R), this gives us

the S-R Bond” (p. 12.). Music teachers should therefore, ensure that a proper utilization of the aforementioned law is put to practice in their classrooms. Pupils and students with cognitive difficulty should always be encouraged with reading activities and any activity that will involve the brain while those with psychomotor challenges should always be engaged in writing activity and playing of musical instruments and other psychomotor activities.

The law of effect as suggested by Vikoo (2015) is “the most famous of the three laws”. This law is based on a pleasure-pain principle, and it states, “if a behavior results in a satisfying state of affair, an increase in behavior preceding the satisfying state will occur” (p. 36). This implies that if the exercise that is carried out by the learner is not rewarded, the stimulus response (S-R) Bond is weakened. Motivation and reinforcement is very essential in the world of education. The pupils and students should be given the privilege to participate in the class fully and afterwards be rewarded in any given task at the course of the lesson. By so doing, they will be motivated and you as a teacher will be able to evaluate their activities.

CONCLUSION/RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusively, it is important and highly recommendable to apply Thorndike’s theory of behavioural learning to music education in regular classrooms. The theory is all encompassing in respect to teaching and learning activities. Some researchers’ analysis and perception has been able to bring to fore the implications of Thorndike’s law of learning on music education. The researchers suggest that it is necessary for music teachers to apply this envious theory in their music classrooms to ensure effective learning experiences.

The study therefore, recommends that music teachers in regular classrooms should ensure proper utilization of the theory in order to achieve an effective music education. The pupils and students should be fully prepared for a new lesson. They should be given ample opportunity to be active in all classroom activities by taking part where necessary. Furthermore, motivation through feedback and reward should be encouraged for an effective music lesson.

REFERENCES

- Hilgard, E.R. and Bower, G.H. (1975). *Theories of learning (4th eds)*. Englewood Cliff, N.J.: Prentice Hall.
- Ofili, D.K. (2018). Music pedagogy for pupils and students with learning disabilities in Christie Toby Inclusive Education Centre, Iriebe, Port Harcourt. An unpublished Dissertation. Nnamdi Azikwie University, Awka.
- Onwuekwe, A.I. (2014). Psychology of music: The law of learning. Unpublished Article, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka.
- Vikoo, B. (2015). *Learning theories and instructional processes (3rd eds)*. Port Harcourt: Pearl Publishers.
- Wikipedia, The Free Encyclopedia (2012). *Inclusive education*. www.wikipedia.com/inclusiveducation. Assessed on the 26th of October, 2016